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A PROSPECTIVE STUDY ON PRESCRIPTION PATTERN IN CONGESTIVE CARDIAC FAILURE

Uthkarsha Vinesh*, Nikhil Kurian, Nivya P.S., Vanendra Yadav S., Nandan H.N., Divya Shree N.

*Bharathi College of Pharmacy, Bharathinagara, K. M. Doddi, Mandya, Karnataka, India – 571422.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Congestive cardiac failure (CCF) is a complex clinical syndrome that results from structural or functional impairment of ventricular filling or ejection of blood, which in turn leads to the cardinal clinical symptoms of dyspnoea and fatigue and signs of CCF namely edema and rales. The incidence and prevalence of CCF is increasing. In India CCF affects younger age group but in western countries it's predominantly a disease of elderly. **Objective:** To study the prescription pattern in congestive cardiac failure in Mandya Institute of Medical Science, Mandya. **Methodology:** This was a cross sectional descriptive study conducted at the department of General Medicine of MIMS. Data was collected from 150 patients under the inclusion criteria. The patients case records, medication charts and other relevant documents were used as a source for data collection. A well designed patient data collection form was used for collecting the details. The information were documented and subjected to suitable statistical methods. **Result:** Total 150 prescriptions with CCF were collected. The mean age was found to be 65.08 ± 14.11 years and male 58% and female 42%. About 573 drugs were prescribed for treating CCF in 150 patients who are included in the study and 90 drugs were given for treating respiratory failure associated with CCF. The drugs prescribed were diuretics (88%), antiplatelet drugs (66%), statin (60%), ACE-inhibitors (50%), β -adrenergic blockers (28%), vasodilators (24%), anticoagulants (18%), sympathomimetic (10%), angiotensin receptor blockers (6%), aldosterone antagonist (2%), cardiac glycosides (2%), PDE-5 inhibitor (2%) and anti-ischaemic metabolic agent (2%). 60% of the total prescriptions under the study contained nebulisation with salbutamol sulphate + ipratropium bromide + budesonide (58%) and salbutamol sulphate + budesonide (2%). Single formulation of two drug combination was given in 24% of the total number of prescriptions which were constituted by atorvastatin + aspirin (18%), atorvastatin + clopidogrel (2%), atorvastatin + fenofibrate (2%), spironolactone + torsemide (2%). 401 (57.8%) of the drugs were received orally, 41 (5.7%) intravenously, 119 (17.9 %) intramuscularly, 27(4.1%) subcutaneously, 6(0.9%) sublingually and 90 (13.2%) drugs by inhalational route. **Conclusion:** Our study concludes that CCF is mostly seen in males and the age group in which it is mostly found is ≥ 65 years. We found that the prescription pattern in congestive cardiac failure vary with inter subject variability and our study concludes that polytherapy was beneficial over monotherapy.

Corresponding author

Uthkarsha Vinesh

D/O VINESH

'Chethana',

Near Over Bridge, Kizhuthally,

PO Thazhechovva,

Kannur, Kerala, India – 670018.

uthkarshavinesh@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Congestive cardiac failure (CCF) is a chronic progressive condition that effects the pumping power of the heart muscles. While often referred to as - heart failure, CCF specifically refers to the stage in which fluid builds up around the heart and causes it to pump inefficiently[1]. CCF is a complex clinical syndrome that results from structural or functional impairment of ventricular filling or ejection of blood, which in turn leads to the cardinal clinical symptoms of dyspnoea and fatigue and signs of CCF namely edema and rales and poor health-related quality of life (HRQoL) [2,3]. With modern therapies, CCF patients are now living longer but with a potentially higher symptom burden that can be worse compared to people with other chronic diseases including cancer [4]. Inadequate symptom control and poor HRQoL are significant drivers of hospitalizations, readmissions, and death in CCF [5,6]. The incidence and prevalence of CCF is increasing. Several large clinical trials have found that pharmacological therapy results in decrease in mortality and morbidity [7]. Drug utilization studies in Congestive cardiac failure (CCF) patients are the powerful exploratory tools to ascertain the role of drugs in the society. Hence periodical auditing of drug utilization pattern in CCF patients is vital for promotion of rational use of drugs, for increasing the therapeutic efficacy, cost effectiveness and for minimizing the adverse effects[2]. The aim of our study is to assess the prescription pattern in patients diagnosed with congestive cardiac failure.

METHODOLOGY

Study population

The study was conducted in 150 patients who have congestive cardiac failure and were admitted in ICU and MICU of Mandya Institute of Medical Science (MIMS) and Teaching Hospital, Mandya which is a 650 bedded hospital.

Study method

This was a six months cross sectional descriptive study in which the data were collected from the patient's case records. The study was approved by Institutional Ethical Committee, MIMS, Mandya. The records of adults (>18 years) who are admitted with congestive cardiac failure to ICU and MICU of MIMS were chosen for the study and the records of patients whose diagnosis was not certain; pregnant or lactating females and patients less than 18 years were excluded from the study.

Statistical analysis:

Descriptive analysis was used to analyse the data. MS Excel and MS Word were used for analysing the data. Qualitative variables were expressed as mean standard deviation and percentage.

RESULTS

Among the 150 patients of congestive cardiac failure studied, 87 (58%) were males and 63 (42%) were females for which the mean age was found to be 65.08 ± 14.11 years.

Table 1: Distribution based on gender of patients.

GENDER	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE OF PATIENTS (%)
MALE	87	58%
FEMALE	63	42%

Figure 1: Gender wise categorization of patients.

The total population when classified into 3 categories of age group, 6 (4%) patients fell into class A, 45 (30%) belonged to class B and 99 (66%) were in class C.

Table 2: Distribution based on age of patients.

CLASS	AGE GROUP (years)	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE OF PATIENTS (%)
A	18-40	6	4
B	40-65	45	30
C	≥65	99	66

Figure 2: Age wise categorization of patients.

PRESCRIPTION PATTERN IN CONGESTIVE CARDIAC FAILURE

About 573 drugs were prescribed for treating CCF in 150 patients who are included in the study and 90 drugs were given for treating respiratory failure associated with CCF. The drugs prescribed were diuretics (88%), antiplatelet drugs (66%), statin (60%), ACE-inhibitors (50%), β -adrenergic blockers (28%), vasodilators (24%), anticoagulants (18%), sympathomimetic (10%), angiotensin receptor blockers (6%), aldosterone antagonist (2%), cardiac glycosides (2%), PDE-5 inhibitor (2%) and anti-ischaemic metabolic agent (2%). Single formulation of two drug combination was given in 24% of the total number of prescriptions which were constituted by atorvastatin + aspirin (18%), atorvastatin + clopidogrel (2%), atorvastatin + fenofibrate (2%), spironolactone + torsemide (2%). 60% of the total prescriptions under the study contained nebulisation with salbutamol sulphate + ipratropium bromide + budesonide (58%) and salbutamol sulphate + budesonide (2%).

TABLE 3: Prescription pattern in congestive cardiac failure.

CLASS OF THE DRUG	NAME OF THE DRUG	NO. OF PRESCRIPTIONS	PERCENTAGE OF PRESCRIPTIONS (%)
CARDIAC GLYCOSIDES	DIGOXIN	3	2
SYMPATHOMIMETICS	DOBUTAMINE	3	2
	DOPAMINE	12	8
DIURETICS	FUROSEMIDE	129	86
	MANNITOL	3	2
ACE INHIBITORS	ENALAPRIL	60	40
	RAMIPRIL	15	10
ANGIOTENSIN RECEPTOR BLOCKERS	LOSARTAN	3	2
	IRBESARTAN	3	2
	TELMISARTAN	3	2
VASODILATORS	GLYCERYL TRINITRATE	24	16
	ISOSORBIDE MONONITRATE	6	4
	ISOSORBIDE DINITRATE	6	4
β -ADRENERGIC BLOCKERS	METOPROLOL	24	16
	CARVEDILOL	12	8
	ATENOLOL	6	4
ALDOSTERONE ANTAGONIST	SPIRINOLACTONE	3	2
STATIN	ATORVASTATIN	90	60
ANTIPLATELET DRUGS	ASPIRIN	51	34
	CLOPIDOGREL	48	32
ANTICOAGULANT	LMWH	27	18
PDE-5 INHIBITOR	PAH	3	2
ANTI ISCHAEMIC METABOLIC AGENT	TRIMETAZIDINE	3	2
COMBINATION DRUGS	SPIRINOLACTONE + TORSEMIDE	3	2
	ATORVASTATIN + ASPIRIN	27	18
	ATORVASTATIN + FENOFIBRATE	3	2
	ATORVASTATIN + CLOPIDOGREL	3	2
NEBULISATION	SALBUTAMOL SULPHATE +	87	58
	IPRATROPIUM BROMIDE +		
	BUDESONIDE		
	SALBUTAMOL SULPHATE +	3	2
	BUDESONIDE		

Figure 3: Prescription pattern in congestive cardiac failure.

ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION OF DRUGS USED IN THE TREATMENT OF CONGESTIVE CARDIAC FAILURE

401 (58.6%) of the drugs were received orally, 41 (6.0%) intravenously, 119 (17.4 %) intramuscularly, 27 (3.9%) subcutaneously, 6 (0.9%) sublingually and 90 (13.2%) drugs by inhalational route.

TABLE 4: Route of administration of drugs used in the treatment of congestive cardiac failure (PO - per oral, INH- inhalation, IV - intravenous, IM - intramuscular, SC - subcutaneous, SL - sublingual).

NAME OF THE DRUG	PO	INH	IV	IM	SC	SL
DIGOXIN	3					
DOBUTAMINE			3			
DOPAMINE			12			
FUROSEMIDE	10			119		
MANNITOL			3			
ENALAPRIL	60					
RAMIPRIL	15					
LOSARTAN	3					
IRBESARTAN	3					
TELMISARTAN	3					
GLYCERYL TRINITRATE			20			4
ISOSORBIDE MONONITRATE	6					
ISOSORBIDE DINITRATE	4					2
METOPROLOL	24					
CARVEDILOL	12					
ATENOLOL	6					
SPIRINOLACTONE	3					
ATORVASTATIN	90					
ASPIRIN	51					
CLOPIDOGREL	48					
LMWH					27	
PAH	3					
TRIMETAZIDINE	3					
SPIRINOLACTONE + TORSEMIDE	3					
ATORVASTATIN + ASPIRIN	27					
ATORVASTATIN + FENOFIBRATE	3					
ATORVASTATIN + CLOPIDOGREL	3					
DUOLIN + BUDECORT		87				
ASTHALIN + BUDECORT		3				
TOTAL	383	90	38	119	27	6
PERCENTAGE (%)	57.8	13.6	5.7	17.9	4.1	0.9

FIGURE 4: Route of drug administration in congestive cardiac failure (PO - per oral, INH- inhalation, IV - intravenous, IM - intramuscular, SC - subcutaneous, SL - sublingual).

TYPE OF DRUG THERAPY USED IN CONGESTIVE CARDIAC FAILURE

Among the 150 prescriptions analysed, one drug only was used in the treatment of CCF in 27 (18%) prescriptions, two drugs were used in 21 (14%) prescriptions, four drugs were used in 36 (24%) prescriptions, five drugs were used in 24 (16%) prescriptions, six drugs were used in 21 (14%) prescriptions, seven drugs in 18 (12%) prescriptions and eight drugs in 3 (2%) prescriptions. Majority of the patients were treated with a diuretic + statin + antiplatelet drug + ACE-inhibitor.

TABLE 5: Type of drug therapy used in CCF.

NUMBER OF DRUGS USED IN THE TREATMENT OF CCF	NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTIONS	PERCENTAGE OF PRESCRIPTIONS (%)
1	27	18
2	21	14
3	0	0
4	36	24
5	24	16
6	21	14
7	18	12
8	3	2

FIGURE 5: Type of drug therapy used in CCF.

DISCUSSION

The records of 150 patients with congestive cardiac failure based on the inclusion criteria in the General Medicine Department of the MIMS were analysed and the mean age was found to be 65.08 ± 14.11 years. Majority of them were male patients i.e., 87 numbers (58%) while the remaining 63 (42%) were female patients.

The population was classified into three classes based on the patient's age as class A, class B, class C which represented the age groups 18-40 years, 40-65 years and ≥ 65 years respectively. 6 (4%) patients fell into class A, 45 (30%) into class B and 99 (66%) were found to fall into class C.

About 573 drugs were prescribed for treating CCF in 150 patients who are included in the study and 90 drugs were given for treating respiratory failure associated with CCF. The drugs prescribed were diuretics (88%), antiplatelet drugs (66%), statin (60%), ACE-inhibitors (50%), β -adrenergic blockers (28%), vasodilators (24%), anticoagulants (18%), sympathomimetic (10%), angiotensin receptor blockers (6%), aldosterone antagonist (2%), cardiac glycosides (2%), PDE-5 inhibitor (2%) and anti-ischaemic metabolic agent (2%). Single formulation of two drug combination was given in 24% of the total number of prescriptions which were constituted by atorvastatin + aspirin (18%), atorvastatin + clopidogrel (2%), atorvastatin + fenofibrate (2%), spironolactone + torsemide (2%). 60% of the total prescriptions under the study contained nebulisation with salbutamol sulphate + ipratropium bromide + budesonide (58%) and salbutamol sulphate + budesonide (2%).

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Among the 150 prescriptions analysed, one drug only was used in the treatment of CCF in 27 (18%) prescriptions, two drugs were used in 21 (14%) prescriptions, four drugs were used in 36 (24%) prescriptions, five drugs were used in 24 (16%) prescriptions, six drugs were used in 21 (14%) prescriptions, seven drugs in 18 (12%) prescriptions and eight drugs in 3 (2%) prescriptions. Majority of the patients were treated with a diuretic + statin + antiplatelet drug + ACE-inhibitor.

CONCLUSION

Our study concludes that congestive cardiac failure is mostly seen in males and the age group in which it is mostly found is ≥ 65 years and it is least in the age group of 18-40 years. A wide range of drugs were used by the patients whose prescriptions were studied among which the most commonly used were diuretics, followed by antiplatelet drugs, statin, ACE-inhibitors, β -blockers, vasodilators, anticoagulants, sympathomimetic, angiotensin receptor blockers, aldosterone antagonist, cardiac glycosides, PDE-5 inhibitor and anti-ischaemic metabolic agent. Among the drugs used to treat respiratory failure associated with CCF were salbutamol sulphate + ipratropium bromide + budesonide and salbutamol sulphate + budesonide. Most of the patients received medications by oral route, followed by intravenous, intramuscular, inhalational, subcutaneous and sublingual routes in that order. Our study concludes that polytherapy was beneficial over monotherapy.

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